

31st International Symposium on Lepton Photon Interactions at High Energies

Tests of Lepton Flavour Universality and searches for Lepton Flavour Violation at LHCb

Biljana Mitreska
TU Dortmund

On behalf of the LHCb collaboration

17-21 July 2023

Abstract

Rare B -hadron decays mediated by $b \rightarrow s\ell\ell$ transitions provide a sensitive test of Lepton Flavour Universality (LFU), a symmetry of the Standard Model by which the coupling of the electroweak gauge bosons to leptons is flavour universal. Extensions of the SM do not necessarily preserve this symmetry and may give sizable contributions to these processes. Precise measurements of LFU ratios are, therefore, an extremely sensitive probe for New Physics. Likewise, breaking of LFU can result in Lepton-Flavour violating decays of the form $b \rightarrow s\ell\ell'$. This talk summarizes recent measurements of Lepton Flavour Universality at LHCb, as well as searches for Lepton-Flavour violating decays.

1 Introduction

Lepton Flavour Universality (LFU) within the Standard Model (SM) of particle physics states that the couplings of gauge bosons are independent of the lepton flavour. Any departure from this concept could lead to a sign of physics beyond the SM (BSM). Powerful probes for testing LFU are $b \rightarrow s\ell\ell$ transitions which occur as flavour changing neutral currents (FCNC) and are suppressed in the SM.

To probe lepton universality ratios of branching fractions of b -hadrons having muons and electrons in their final states are used, defined as

$$\mathcal{R}_{H_s} = \frac{\int_{q_{min}^2}^{q_{max}^2} \frac{d\Gamma(H_b \rightarrow H_s \mu^+ \mu^-)}{dq^2} dq^2}{\int_{q_{min}^2}^{q_{max}^2} \frac{d\Gamma(H_b \rightarrow H_s e^+ e^-)}{dq^2} dq^2}, \quad (1)$$

where q^2 is the squared dilepton invariant mass. An advantage in using ratios as observables is that they are not affected by hadronic uncertainties that come from modelling of the form factors, particularly affecting the the branching fractions, and presence of $c\bar{c}$ loops. While these observables provide a robust test of LFU there has been a range of measurements using branching fractions and angular observables that report tensions with the SM. Values below the SM are reported in branching fractions measurements in $B \rightarrow K^* \mu^+ \mu^-$ and $B_s \rightarrow \phi \mu^+ \mu^-$ [1, 5, 9]. In addition the angular analyses performed in $B \rightarrow K^* \mu^+ \mu^-$ and $B_s \rightarrow \phi \mu^+ \mu^-$ report deviations in a set of angular observables in the low q^2 regime [7, 6, 8]. Extensions of the SM explaining these measurements have been proposed [16, 11, 12] which discuss models with heavy BSM particles. Many BSM models suggest the existence of lepton flavour violating (LFV) decays. They are forbidden in the SM and sensitive to specific BSM scenarios that include models with scalar or vector leptoquarks [15, 14] and as well models with Z' bosons [13]. Any observation of LFU violation or LFV decays involving charged leptons can be a clear sign of BSM physics. These proceedings give an overview of the simultaneous $\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{K}}$ and $\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{K}^*}$ measurement and cover the searches for lepton flavour violating decays in $b \rightarrow s\ell\ell$ transitions.

2 Simultaneous measurement of $\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{K}}$ and $\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{K}^*}$

This is the first simultaneous measurement of the $\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{K}}$ and $\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{K}^*}$ (ratios defined as in Eq.1) by LHCb [4, 2]. It uses $B^+ \rightarrow K^{+\ell^+ \ell^-}$ and $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0 \ell^+ \ell^-}$ decays, where ℓ can be a muon or electron and the K^* meson is reconstructed with a $K^+ \pi^-$ final state. The observables $\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{K}}$ and $\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{K}^*}$ are measured in two q^2 intervals: $0.1 < q^2 < 1.1$ GeV² (low q^2) and $1.1 < q^2 < 6.0$ GeV² (high q^2) and are calculated as double ratio with the relation

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{R}_{(K/K^*)} &= \frac{\mathcal{B}(B^{(+,0)} \rightarrow K^{(+,*0)} \mu^+ \mu^-)}{\mathcal{B}(B^{(+,0)} \rightarrow K^{(+,*0)} e^+ e^-)} \times \frac{\mathcal{B}(B^{(+,0)} \rightarrow K^{(+,*0)} J/\psi(e^+ e^-))}{\mathcal{B}(B^{(+,0)} \rightarrow K^{(+,*0)} J/\psi(\mu^+ \mu^-))} \\ &= \left(\frac{N_{K^{(+,*0)} \mu^+ \mu^-}}{N_{K^{(+,*0)} e^+ e^-}} \right) \left(\frac{N_{K^{(+,*0)} J/\psi(e^+ e^-)}}{N_{K^{(+,*0)} J/\psi(\mu^+ \mu^-)}} \right) \\ &\times \left(\frac{\epsilon_{K^{(+,*0)} e^+ e^-}}{\epsilon_{K^{(+,*0)} \mu^+ \mu^-}} \right) \left(\frac{\epsilon_{K^{(+,*0)} J/\psi(\mu^+ \mu^-)}}{\epsilon_{K^{(+,*0)} J/\psi(e^+ e^-)}} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where N and ϵ are the yields and efficiencies of the respective decays. The double ratio ensures maximum cancellation of systematic effects in efficiencies in the electron and muon channels. Resonant decays of the form $B^{+ / 0} \rightarrow K^{+ / *0} J/\psi (\rightarrow \ell^+ \ell^-)$ are used for calibrating the efficiencies. The yields are extracted from a simultaneous fit to the invariant mass distribution of the respective decays. The reconstruction

of the signal candidates involves combination of a K or a K^* meson with two opposite charged leptons (e or μ). An experimental challenge of this measurement is the reconstruction of electrons, since they have different signatures than muons in the LHCb detector. The first difference arises at the hardware trigger level (L0) which employs different threshold regarding the transverse momentum (p_t) that leads to reduced efficiencies for electron candidates. To reduce the impact of the different hardware triggers the trigger strategy was optimized to minimize the differences in trigger efficiencies of muons and electrons. In addition, electrons emit bremsstrahlung photons when traversing through material which results with degradation of the mass resolution as compared to muons. A recovery algorithm designed to search for photons compatible with being emitted from the reconstructed electron is applied. In spite of having the recovery in place, the mass resolution of the decays involving electrons is degraded compared with decays of muons allowing higher background pollution that requires careful modelling. To separate the combinatorial background from the signal a classifier that employs the geometric and vertex properties of the signal candidate and its final state particles is trained. Another classifier is trained to separate the signal from the partially reconstructed backgrounds of the form $B \rightarrow K^{+/*0} \ell^+ \ell^- X$ where in addition to the geometric and vertex features the isolation of the final state particles is used. Many of the backgrounds coming from semileptonic decays ($B \rightarrow D \ell \nu_\ell$) and backgrounds arising from misidentification of a hadron to lepton that cause the resonant modes to be misidentified as signal have been removed through applying vetoes connected with particle identification (PID) and kinematics. The last remaining background is the misidentified backgrounds of a lepton with hadron such as for example electron with kaons or pions. This background is modelled with a data-driven approach starting with background enriched samples (with inverted PID criteria). Furthermore the mass spectra in this case are weighted according to the probability of the misidentified contribution to pass the specific PID cut and the signal contribution is subtracted. The resulting invariant mass shape is used for modelling this background in the final fit to data.

Calibration of the simulation is done in order to improve the compatibility to data. It is done in sequential reweighting that accounts for differences due to the PID and track performance, event multiplicity and trigger efficiency. To validate the overall analysis procedure a cross check is done via measuring $r_{J/\psi}^{(K, K^*)} = \frac{\mathcal{B}(B^{(+/0)} \rightarrow K^{(+,*0)} J/\psi(\mu^+ \mu^-))}{\mathcal{B}(B^{(+/0)} \rightarrow K^{(+,*0)} J/\psi(e^+ e^-))}$ and $r_{\Psi(2S)}^{(K, K^*)} = \frac{\mathcal{B}(B^{(+/0)} \rightarrow K^{(+,*0)} \Psi(2S)(\mu^+ \mu^-))}{\mathcal{B}(B^{(+/0)} \rightarrow K^{(+,*0)} \Psi(2S)(e^+ e^-))} \times r_{J/\psi}^{-1}$. Computing $r_{J/\psi}$ directly probes the residual misalignments in simulation efficiencies of electrons against muons and $r_{\Psi(2S)}$ helps to validate that any residual imperfections in efficiencies cancel in the double ratio. The values are found to be compatible up to two standard deviations with the SM value of unity. The final fit to data is done simultaneously in the two q^2 regions and for the two observables and the two data taking periods of LHCb (Run 1 and Run 2). The invariant mass fits for the muon and electron modes are shown on Fig.1 and Fig.2, respectively. The measured values for the ratios are given as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{R}_K(\text{low } q^2) &= 0.994_{-0.082}^{+0.90}(\text{stat})_{-0.027}^{+0.029}(\text{syst}) \\
 \mathcal{R}_{K^*}(\text{low } q^2) &= 0.927_{-0.087}^{+0.093}(\text{stat})_{-0.035}^{+0.036}(\text{syst}) \\
 \mathcal{R}_K(\text{central } q^2) &= 0.949_{-0.041}^{+0.042}(\text{stat})_{-0.022}^{+0.022}(\text{syst}) \\
 \mathcal{R}_{K^*}(\text{central } q^2) &= 1.027_{-0.068}^{+0.072}(\text{stat})_{-0.026}^{+0.027}(\text{syst}).
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

The results are statistically dominated with the highest systematics coming from the modelling of the misidentified backgrounds. The measurements are consistent with the SM and present the most precise test of LFU using $b \rightarrow s \ell \ell$ transitions.

Figure 1: Distributions of invariant mass in $K^+\mu^+\mu^-$ (left) and $K^+\pi^-\mu^+\mu^-$ (right) in the low q^2 (top), central q^2 (middle) and the resonant control decay (bottom) [4, 2].

Figure 2: Distributions of invariant mass in $K^+e^+e^-$ and $K^+\pi^-e^+e^-$ in the low q^2 (top), central q^2 (middle) and the resonant control decay (bottom) [4, 2].

3 Lepton Flavour Violation measurements

3.1 Search for $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \mu^\pm e^\mp$ and $B_s \rightarrow \phi \mu^\pm e^\mp$

The LHCb collaboration has performed searches for lepton flavour violating decays in $b \rightarrow s \ell \ell$ transitions in the decays of $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \mu^\pm e^\mp$ and $B_s^0 \rightarrow \phi \mu^\pm e^\mp$ using the full dataset corresponding to a total luminosity of 9 fb^{-1} [10]. The signal candidates were reconstructed with $K^+ \pi^- \mu^\pm e^\mp$ and $K^+ K^- \mu^\pm e^\mp$. The signal yield is obtained from a fit to the $B_{(s)}^0$ invariant mass which is then used to calculate the branching fraction following as

$$\mathcal{B} = \frac{\mathcal{B}_{norm}}{N_{norm}} \times \frac{\epsilon_{norm}}{\epsilon_{signal}} \times N_{sig}, \quad (4)$$

with \mathcal{B}_{norm} and N_{norm} denoting the branching fraction and yield of the normalisation modes $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi(\rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-) K^{*0}$ and $B_s^0 \rightarrow J/\psi(\rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-) \phi$. Specific vetoes were applied for contributions originating from semileptonic decays of the form $B \rightarrow D^{(*)} \ell \nu$ and as well for backgrounds of misidentified b hadrons and leptons. Combinatorial background is suppressed using a Boosted Decision Tree (BDT) classifier, where the candidates in the upper mass sideband between 5600-7600 MeV are used as a training proxy for the combinatorial background. No significant signal has been observed and upper limits of the branching fractions are determined at 90(95) % confidence level, resulting in

$$\mathcal{B}(B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} e^+ \mu^-) < 6.8(7.9) \times 10^{-9}, \quad (5)$$

$$\mathcal{B}(B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} e^- \mu^+) < 5.7(6.9) \times 10^{-9}, \quad (6)$$

$$\mathcal{B}(B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} e^\pm \mu^\mp) < 10.1(11.7) \times 10^{-9}, \quad (7)$$

$$\mathcal{B}(B_s^0 \rightarrow \phi e^\pm \mu^\mp) < 16.0(19.8) \times 10^{-9}. \quad (8)$$

The results are determined using a phase-space decay model and represent the most stringent limits in these decay modes to date. In addition, exclusion limits are reported for a scalar ($C_S^{\mu e} \neq 0$) and a left-handed ($C_9^{\mu e} = -C_{10}^{\mu e}$) BSM scenario [10].

3.2 Search for $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^\pm \mu^\mp$

A first search for the $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^\pm \mu^\mp$ decay was performed by LHCb using the full dataset of 9 fb^{-1} [3]. The K^* meson is reconstructed with K^+ and π^- and the τ lepton is reconstructed with $\pi^- \pi^+ \pi^- (\pi^0) \nu_\tau$. Not being able to reconstruct the neutrino in the final state results in a non peaking invariant mass. Therefore, the signal yield was measured via a fit to the corrected mass $m_{corr} = \sqrt{p_\perp^2 + m_{K^* \tau \mu}^2} + p_\perp$, where p_\perp is the momentum perpendicular to the direction of the B meson. When calculating the branching fraction $B^0 \rightarrow D^-(K^+ \pi^- \pi^-) D_s^+(K^+ K^- \pi^+)$ decay is used as normalisation mode. The combinatorial background is suppressed by using a BDT and contributions from $B \rightarrow D^* \tau(\mu) \nu$ decays are vetoed. The final fit to the corrected mass does not show significant signal and upper limits of the branching fractions at 90(95)% are set as

$$\mathcal{B}(B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^+ \mu^-) < 1.0(1.2) \times 10^{-5}, \quad (9)$$

$$\mathcal{B}(B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^- \mu^+) < 8.2(9.8) \times 10^{-6}, \quad (10)$$

representing the most stringent limits in $b \rightarrow s \tau \mu$ transitions.

4 Conclusions

Rare b -decays are excellent probes of the SM and searching for BSM effects. When probing the SM with $b \rightarrow s \ell \ell$ transitions the LHCb collaboration has provided the

most precise LFU test measuring the \mathcal{R}_K and \mathcal{R}_{K^*} . Furthermore, searches for lepton flavour violating decays which are important checks for BSM physics, result with the most stringent upper limits measured by LHCb. The ongoing physics programme at LHCb is aiming to further perform angular analyses and as well ratios of branching fractions in various $b \rightarrow s\ell\ell$ transitions. The data collected during Run 3 will help to reduce the statistical uncertainties allowing for more precise LFU measurements.

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